

Work-Life Balance and Perceived Stress among Married and Unmarried Female IT Employees

V. Rajalakshmi and U.L. Bhuvaneshwari

Department of Psychology, Government Arts College, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu

In the emerging career advancement and competition era of information technology, maintaining work-life balance is challenging for female IT employees because they need to balance both work and home environments simultaneously. So, due to the multiple roles and responsibilities with the limited resources, they experience a high level of stress. The present study investigated the relationship and differences between work-life balance and perceived stress among married and unmarried female IT employees. For this purpose, a sample of 100 female IT employees (50 married & 50 unmarried) has been selected as participants. They were administered using the Work-Life Balance Scale (Hayman, 2011) and the Perceived Stress Scale (Cohen et al., 1983). The collected data were analyzed using Karl Pearson correlation and independent sample t-test, and the findings suggested that work-life balance is negatively associated with perceived stress, and married female employees struggle to balance both work and family together, and they exhibit a greater percentage of perceived stress.

Keywords: Work-life balance, perceived stress, married and unmarried and IT employees

In the past decade, IT (Information technology) has developed rapidly, which made changes in working hours and job demands of employees. Especially among female employees, because female employees try to balance both home and work environments with limited resources and time (Strazdins et al., 2011). Theoretically, the Role Strain theory (Goode, 1960) discusses that individuals who have multiple roles to deal with lack time and resources, so they tend have more stress.

Work-life balance is known as the ability to manage both work and family's requirements without having role conflict, and perceived stress is referred to as the subjective experience of unpredictable life situations. (Cohen et al., 1983)

Recent research work highlighted that not having a good work-life balance leads to stress. Greenhaus and Allen (2011) highlighted that an improper balance between work and family promotes emotional outbursts and high stress among working populations. Also, Employees with good work-life balance experience low stress and good mental well-being (Haar et al., 2014).

Married female employees in the IT field who have both professional and personal demands are more likely to experience high stress (Matthew & Panchanathan, 2011). Furthermore, research revealed that married working women shown high work life conflict and stress than unmarried female employees (Mathew & Panchanathan, 2011) and Kossek, Lewis and Hammer (2010) considered marital status as a vital factor that contributes to increased

levels of stress.

The present study aimed to find out the interplay and difference in work-life balance and perceived stress among married as well as unmarried female IT employees.

Review of Literature

The study on government and private college employees by Arora et al. (2021) found a significant gender difference in the level of their life quality, balance in work and life and stress.

Dhiman (2022) examined work-life balance in IT employees during the pandemic. The results showed that work-from-home conditions made them feel stressed, and they were unable to devote time to their family and friends due to excessive work pressure.

Saya (2024) is interested in knowing the interplay of stress and work-life balance. The study found no significant correlation between these variables.

Upendar et al. (2025) did a comparative study among pharmacy and engineering students in perceived stress. The finding revealed that pharmacy students have a low level of stress compared to engineering students.

Budhathoki (2025) investigated how work-life balance impacts the stress and performance of the working population. The result showed that neglecting personal life promotes stress, which affects an individual's health and performance.

From the above literature, it is evident that work-life balance and perceived stress are globally recognized challenges for working women, especially the unique pressure of the IT industry, reinforced by female marital responsibility, so it is crucial to address the problem and support their well-being.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the relationship between work-life balance and perceived stress.
- To know the difference between married and unmarried female IT employees in Work -Life balance and Perceived stress.

Author Note

V. Rajalakshmi, Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Psychology
Government Arts College, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu
Dr. U.L. Bhuvaneshwari, Associate Professor and Head, Department
of Psychology, Government Arts College, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu
We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.
Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to
V. Rajalakshmi, Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Psychology
Government Arts College, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu
E-mail: rajalakshmicareer.1997@gmail.com

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*- There will be a significant relationship between Work-Life balance and perceived stress among married and unmarried female IT employees.
- *H2*- There will be a significant difference in the level of Work Life balance and Perceived stress among married and unmarried female IT employees.

Method

Participants

The sample consisted of 100 (Unmarried 50 & Married - 50) female IT employees in Coimbatore. The purposive sampling technique was employed to select the appropriate participants. This sampling technique helps to select a specific group of respondents rather than the general population.

Inclusion Criteria

- Employees with a minimum of 1 year of experience
- Full-time employees
- Married female IT employees
- Unmarried female IT employees
- Participants in the age range of 21 to 40 years
- Participants who are willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Female employees who are separated, divorced or widowed were excluded.
- Participants with severe physical and mental issues.

Informed Consent

Before the data collection, all the participants were briefed on the research objectives of the study and they were informed that their participation was based on informed consent and that their data information will be kept confidential and solely used for research purposes.

Measures

Socio-demographic Sheet: This data sheet was formulated by the researcher to gather socio-demographic details such as age, work experience, marital status and annual income.

Work-Life Balance Scale: The Work-Life Balance was constructed by Hayman (2005). This scale has 15 items in total with a 5-point Likert scale. It has reverse scoring and 3 subscales, namely, 1. Work interference with personal life, 2. Personal life interference with work, and 3. Work/ Personal life enhancement. This scale demonstrated great internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha of 0.70 and 0.80, and construct validity. In this scale, greater scores indicate a good work-life balance.

Perceived Stress Scale: The perceived stress designed by Cohen et al in 1983. This scale has 10 items in total with 5-Point Likert scale. The Cronbach's alpha reliability was 0.84, and the criterion validity.

Procedure

The data was collected in various Information technology organizations from Coimbatore. Prior permission was obtained from the HR departments of the organizations, and before the administration of the tool, rapport was built and the aim of the study was elaborated. They were assured that the collected information

would be used solely for research objectives.

The personal data sheet and questionnaire were administered to them and they were instructed to respond to them. Once they completed the questionnaire, scoring was carried out and the collected data were coded and entered into SPSS 27.0 version to make further analysis.

Statistical Analysis

In the present study, the data were analyzed using the Karl Pearson correlation to determine the relationship between the study variables and an independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the mean score of work-life balance and perceived stress.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics and Pearson Correlation between Work-life Balance and Perceived Stress among Female IT Employees

Variable	Mean	SD	Work-life Balance	Perceived Stress
Work-life Balance	47.48	15.68	1	-0.61***
Perceived Stress	22.44	7.02	-0.61***	1

Note. *** $p < .001$

As shown in Table 1, a significant Negative correlation was found between work-life balance and perceived stress ($r = -0.61, p < .001$). Hence, it is evident that female IT employees with good work-life balance experience a low level of perceived stress. So, the hypothesis "H1- There will be a significant relationship between Work Life balance and Perceived stress among married and unmarried female IT employees." is accepted.

Table 2

Group Differences in Work-life Balance and Perceived Stress among Female IT Employees

Variable	Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	t	p
Work Life Balance	Married	50	32.26	6.16	27.58	<.001
	Unmarried	50	62.70	4.80		
Perceived Stress	Married	50	27.24	6.01	7.94	<.001
	Unmarried	50	17.64	6.08		

Note. $p < .001$

As shown in Table 2, significant differences were found among married and unmarried female IT employees in work-life balance and perceived stress. Married female IT employees showed a low level of worklife balance and a higher level of perceived stress ($p < .001$). Therefore, the hypothesis "H2- There will be a significant difference in the level of Work Life balance and Perceived stress among married and unmarried female IT employees" is accepted.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that work-life balance had a moderate inverse relationship ($r = -.61, p < .001$) with perceived stress among married and unmarried female IT employees. Due to the long working hours and constant job demands, they have an imbalance in both personal and work responsibilities, which may lead to stress in their daily lives. These finding like the study of Prasad et al. (2020). They discussed higher workload in the IT industries significantly increases perceived stress. Furthermore, A

significant difference found in an independent t-test revealed that married and unmarried female IT employees have significant differences in their level of work-life balance and perceived stress. It is because married female employees have family responsibilities and multiple roles with work-related tasks, so all these things reduce their personal time and leaving a source to experience stress. This result is supported by Role strain theory (Goode, 1960) which illustrates that an individual feel high level of stress while having multiple roles to deal with. Meanwhile, unmarried female employees experience a low level of stress and have a good work-life balance because they have fewer family responsibilities compared to married female employees. Research by Singh et al. (2021) also found the same that unmarried female tends to have lower stress due to the lack of multiple responsibilities.

So, the higher perceived stress level in married female IT employees suggested the need for promoting work-life balance, flexible work hours and supportive workplace practices and policies to enhance the mental well-being of married female IT employees.

Conclusion

The present study concluded that a significant negative correlation was found between work-life balance and perceived stress among female IT employees. It suggests that an improvement is needed in work-life balance to reduce stress. Additionally, a significant difference was found in work life and balance and perceived stress in them. So, these findings addressed the need for organizational policies and a support system to help and working women improve their psychological well-being.

Limitations of the Study

- Only female IT employees were included.
- Only married and unmarried female employees were included.
- Marital status alone was considered
- Low sample size.

References

Arora, K., Shekhawant, K., & Sethi, S.R. (2021). Work-life balance, perceived stress and quality of life among government and private sector employees during Covid-19. *International Journal of Education, Modern Management, Applied Science and Social Science*, 03(1), 82-88.

- Budhathoki, R., Pandey, D., & Shukla, J. (2025). Impact of work life balance on stress level and performance. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 13(2), 4781-4791. DIP:18.01.422.20251302, DOI:10.25215/1302.422
- Cohen, S., Kamarck, T., & Mermelstein, R. (1983). A global measure of perceived stress. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 24(4), 385-396. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2136404>
- Dhiman, A. (2022). Work-life balance in the shadow of the pandemic- with due consideration to IT companies. *AKGEC International Journal of Technology*, 13(2), 20-21. NICE School of Business Studies, Shobhit Institute of Engineering and Technology (Deemed to be University).
- Goode, W. J. (1960). A theory of role strain. *American Sociological Review*, 25(4), 483-496. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2092930>
- Greenhaus, J. H., & Allen, T. D. (2011). Workfamily balance: A review and extension of the literature. In J. C. Quick and L. E. Tetrick (Eds.), *Handbook of occupational health psychology* (2nd ed., pp. 165-183). American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/12275-009>
- Haar, J. M., Russo, M., Suñe, A., & Ollier-Malaterre, A. (2014). Outcomes of worklife balance on job satisfaction, life satisfaction, and mental health: A study across seven cultures. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 85(3), 361-373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2014.08.010>
- Hayman, J. (2005, September). *Psychometric development of a Work-life Balance Scale* [Paper presentation]. British Academy of Management Conference, Harrogate, UK.
- Kammampati, U., Keerthi, K., Ashritha, M., Vignandath, M., & Prasanna, G. (2025). Perceived stress and its determinants among a private pharmacy and engineering college students: A comparative study. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 13(4), 1214-1225. DIP:18.01.111.20251304, DOI:10.25215/1304.111
- Kossek, E. E., Lewis, S., & Hammer, L. B. (2010). Worklife initiatives and organizational change: Overcoming mixed messages to move from the margin to the mainstream. *Human Relations*, 63(1), 3-19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726709352385>
- Mathew, A. A., & Panchanathan, A. D. (2011). An empirical study on work-life balance of women entrepreneurs in South India. *Emerging Trends in Business Management*, 1-12.
- Prasad, K. D. V., Vaidya, R. W., & Mangipudi, M. R. (2020). Effect of occupational stress and remote working on psychological well-being of employees: An empirical study during Covid-19 pandemic with reference to the information technology industry in Hyderabad. *Indian Journal of Commerce and Management Studies*, 11(2), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.18843/ijcms/v11i2/01>
- Saya, A. (2024). Relationship between stress and work-life balance. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 12(2), 4762-4768. DIP:18.01.425.20241202, DOI:10.25215/1202.425
- Singh, A. K., Singh, S., & Singh, V. K. (2021). A study on work-life balance and its impact on job satisfaction among working women. *Journal of Management Research and Analysis*, 8(2), 84-89. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.jmra.2021.01>
- Strazdins, L., O'Brien, L. V., Lucas, N., & Rodgers, B. (2013). Combining work and family: Rewards or risks for children's mental health? *Social Science and Medicine*, 87, 99-107.

Received February 1, 2026

Revision received February 19, 2026

Accepted February 20, 2026